

Heats of Ionization of Water in Glycerol+ Water, t-butanol+ Water and Dioxane+ Water Mixtures and Comparison of the Thermodynamics of Ionization of Water in Different Mixed Solvents

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The heats of ionization for the reaction $2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{OH}^-$ have been determined calorimetrically in several mixed solvents viz. t-butanol+ water, glycerol + water and dioxane + water mixtures. The data for the heats of ionization in methanol + water, ethanol + water, ethyleneglycol + water and dimethyl sulphoxide + water have been taken from the literature for comparison. The heats of ionization data have been coupled with appropriate free energy data where available to calculate the entropy changes in different solvent systems. A critical evaluation of the different factors affecting the thermodynamics of ionization in different mixed solvents have been made in terms of ion-solvent interactions and structural aspects. The limitations for the proper interpretation of the thermodynamics have been stressed.

AN understanding of the role of solvents and the related solute-solvent interactions on the acid-base equilibria and other thermodynamic properties necessitates the study of the auto ionization processes of water in different mixed solvents at different temperatures. The variation of the auto protolysis constants with different solvent compositions provides a measure of acid-base properties and particularly the scale of pH in different solutions.

We present in this communication a comparison of the enthalpies of ionization of water in different mixed solvents (methanol + water, ethanol + water, t-butanol + water, ethyleneglycol + water, glycerol + water, dioxane + water and dimethyl sulphoxide + water) of widely divergent characters. Though methanol, ethanol and t-butanol are hydrogen-bonded monohydric alcohols, the latter is conspicuously known for its anomalous behaviour with relatively low dielectric constant. Ethylene-glycol and glycerol with two and three hydroxyl groups have properties distinctly different from monohydric alcohols.

Dioxane and dimethylsulphoxide are non-hydrogen bonded solvent systems with relatively low and high dielectric constants.

In the present work, we determined the heats of ionization of water

in t-butanol + water, glycerol + water and dioxane + water systems. The data for the heats of ionization in methanol + water¹, ethanol + water², ethylene glycol + water³ and dimethylsulphoxide + water^{4,5} were taken from the literature for comparison.

The heats of ionization data have been coupled with appropriate free energy data⁶⁻⁸ where available to calculate the entropy changes in different solvent systems.

A critical evaluation of the different aspects of the thermodynamics of ionization in different mixed solvents have been made.

Experimental

Dioxane was purified in the way described before⁹. t-butanol (S.D 'S laboratory reagent) was heated with lime, kept overnight and distilled. The distillate was crystallized and the supernatant liquor was rejected. The crystallized mass was melted and was finally distilled.

Glycerol (E. Merck) was distilled under vacuum which corresponds to a purity of 99.97%.

The weight percentages of the organic solvents in mixed solvents and their dielectric constants were obtained by mixing the calculated amounts of the two

solvents and comparing the density values of the mixed solvents with the reported density values^{10,11}.

Perchloric acid and caustic soda were of analar grade and estimated in the usual way. All solutions were made with double-distilled water from an all-glass distilling set.

The details of the calorimeter used have been reported in an earlier communication¹². For the enthalpy change measurements, 250 ml of HClO₄ solution (~2 × 10⁻² M) in appropriate solvents was taken in the reaction flask. In glass bulbs, definite volume of alkali (5 ml of ~0.2 M NaOH solution), well in excess of the amount required to ensure complete neutralization of the acid, was taken in appropriate solvents to avoid heat change due to mixing. After proper equilibration at the desired temperature, the bulb was broken and heat change was measured by the change in resistances which was calibrated against known heat supplied before each set of measurement. Suitable blank titrations were performed to measure heat of dilution of concentrated alkali which was subtracted from the heat of neutralization data.

The measurements were done at 25°.

From the measured heat liberated, the enthalpy changes were calculated from the relation

$$\Delta H = -\frac{Q}{x} \quad (2)$$

where Q is the heat liberated in Cal to neutralise x moles of HClO₄ acid.

The results are given in tables 1-3.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMICS OF IONIZATION OF WATER IN DIFFERENT MIXED SOLVENTS AT 25°
t-BuOH + H₂O mixtures

wt % of t-BuOH	pK _{a/a} *	ΔG _s ^o (KCal/mole)	ΔH ^o (KCal/mole)	-TΔS ^o (KCal/mole)
10	14.23	19.46	14.38 (±0.06)	5.08
20	14.54	19.82	15.06 (±0.06)	4.76
30	14.74	20.09	15.44 (±0.07)	4.65
40	14.98	20.42	16.18 (±0.06)	4.24
50	15.28	20.83	17.01 (±0.08)	3.82
60	—	—	17.70 (±0.05)	—
70	—	—	18.53 (±0.07)	—

(* interpolated values from ref. 7)

TABLE 2—DIOXAN + WATER MIXTURES

wt % of dioxan	p _{a/a} *	ΔG _s ^o (KCal/mole)	ΔH ^o (KCal/mole)	-TΔS ^o (KCal/mole)
10	14.28	19.46	13.51 (±0.06)	5.95
20	14.58	19.87 (19.94) ⁺	13.75(13.52) ⁺ (±0.6)	6.12
30	14.88	20.28	15.02(±0.04)	5.26
40	15.26	20.80	15.32(±0.05)	5.48
45	—	(21.47) ⁺	—(13.19) ⁺	—
50	15.71	21.41	15.03(±0.10)	6.38
60	16.12	21.97	15.63(±0.07)	6.34
70	—	(24.35) ⁺	16.03(12.66) ⁺ (±0.06)	—

(*interpolated values from ref. 7, + values in brackets from ref. 29)

TABLE 3—GLYCEROL—WATER MIXTURES

wt % of glycerol	ΔH ^o (KCal/mole)
10	11.13 (±0.08)
20	10.63 (±0.07)
30	11.36 (±0.06)
40	11.49 (±0.04)
50	12.02 (±0.08)
60	12.47 (±0.08)

TABLE 4—METHANOL—WATER MIXTURES

wt % MeOH	pK ^o s/m (molal)	ΔG _s ^o KCal mole ⁻¹	ΔH ^o KCal mole ⁻¹	-TΔS ^o KCal mole ⁻¹
0	13.997 (14.00)*	19.095	13.34	5.76
10	14.037 (14.04)	19.151	12.56	6.59
20	14.055 (14.07)	19.175	11.62	7.56
28.5	14.067	19.192	10.78	8.41
50	14.097 (14.13)	19.233	8.85	10.38
60	14.127 (14.15)	19.273	8.07	11.20
70	14.218 (14.19)	19.398	7.33	12.07
80	14.423 (14.30)	19.677	6.72	12.96
90	14.845 (15.07)	20.253	6.46	13.79
100	16.708 (16.71)	22.795	10.70	12.10

(* values in brackets from ref. 8)

TABLE 5—DMSO—WATER MIXTURES^{4,5}

Temp—25°	X _{DMSO}	pK _{a/a}	ΔG° KCal/mole	ΔH° KCal/mole	-TΔS° KCal/mole
	0	14.00	19.10	13.37	5.73
	0.1	14.79	20.18	14.78	5.40
	0.2	15.64	21.34	12.46	8.88
	0.3	16.43	22.41	11.31	11.10
	0.4	17.26	23.55	11.04	12.51
	0.5	18.21	24.84	9.09	15.75
	0.6	19.09	26.04	11.09	14.95
	0.7	19.89	27.13	15.45	11.68
	0.8	20.54	28.03	18.68	9.35

TABLE 6—EtOH+ WATER MIXTURES^{2,7}

wt % of EtOH	pK _{a/a}	ΔG _s (KCal/mole)	ΔH° (KCal/mole)	-TΔS° (KCal/mole)
0	14.00	19.10	13.3	5.80
10	14.20 (14.00)	19.36	13.6	5.76
20	14.37 (14.02)	19.59	13.6	5.99
30	14.49 (14.03)	19.75	13.3	6.45
40	14.66 (14.04)	19.98	12.4	7.58
50	14.78 (14.05)	20.14	11.4	8.74
60	— (14.09)	—	10.3	—
70	— (14.13)	—	8.8	—
80	— (14.22)	—	7.2	—
90	— (14.79)	—	5.3	—
95	—	—	5.2	—
100	— (18.88)	—	—	—

(* values in brackets from ref. 8)

TABLE 7—ETHYLENE GLYCOL+ WATER⁸

wt % of ethylene glycol	pK _{s/m}	pK _{a/a}	ΔG _s (KCal/-mole)	ΔH° (KCal/-mole)	-TΔS° (KCal/-mole)
10	13.85	13.85	18.89	12.43	6.46
20	—	13.69	—	—	—
30	13.72	13.58	18.74	10.92	7.82
40	—	13.48	—	—	—
50	13.66	13.40	18.62	9.85	8.77
60	—	13.34	—	—	—
70	13.82	—	18.75	9.35	9.40
90	14.37	—	19.59	9.34	10.25

(* interpolated values from ref. 7)

Discussion

The equilibrium constants for the reaction

have been defined in different ways depending on the choice of standard states. These are

$$(1) K_{a/1} = C_{H^+} + C_{OH^-} \cdot f_{\pm}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$(2) K_{a/a} = \frac{C_{H^+} \cdot C_{OH^-} \cdot f_{\pm}^2}{a_w} = \frac{K_{a/1}}{a_w} \quad (5)$$

$$(3) K_{a/o} = K_{a/1}/c_w \quad (6)$$

$$(4) K_{m/1} = m_{H^+} \cdot m_{OH^-} \cdot r_{\pm}^2 \quad (7)$$

pK_{a/1} and pK_{m/1} are related by

$$pK_{a/1} = pK_{m/1} - 2 \log d \quad (8)$$

The differences in pK values in mixed solvents in different units are very small (except for pK_{a/o} units). The trends remain the same whatever may be units chosen. We preferred the use of the same units as used by different authors though Woolley *et al*⁷ preferred to use pK_{a/o} for comparison. But it is desirable to use the mole-fraction units which is seldom done in practice.

The values of pK_s (pK values in different solvents as determined by different workers) and other thermodynamic properties (ΔG, ΔH and TΔS) in different mixed solvents are given in tables 1-7.

Ohtaki⁸ prefers to calculate autoprotolysis constants of water assuming that a proton is hydrated with four water molecules in water and is solvated with one amphiprotic solvent molecule in the solvent and no mixed solvated proton exists in a mixed solvent. The pK_s values reported by Ohtaki are in good agreement with the interpolated values from Koskikallio⁶ for methanol+water mixtures upto about 80 wt % of methanol beyond which there are deviations. But, for ethanol-water mixtures the values given by Ohtaki deviates considerably from the values reported by Woolley *et al*⁷. and appear to be in error.

As expected, in all the solvent mixtures pK_s and hence ΔG gradually increases as the concentration of organic solvent (except in ethylene glycol+water mixtures where a minimum is observed near 50% w/w) increases due to lowering of dielectric constant. However, the change in pK_s values in different solvents clearly indicates that other factors besides dielectric constants are important to explain the variations. The plots of pK against 1/D for different solvent mixtures give straight lines with different slopes and intercepts indicating that the interactions are different in different solvent systems which is natural to expect due to

changed solute-solvent interactions and solvent basicity.¹³ Structural contributions would not affect ΔG much due to compensating effects of ΔH and $T\Delta S$. Solvent basicity may be important but it is not clear how and to what extent it affects ΔG . The basicity of solvents in the gaseous phase are in the order¹⁴

In solution the basicity may well change. However, it is known that MeOH-H₂O, EtOH-H₂O and t-BuOH-H₂O mixtures are generally more basic than water¹⁵⁻¹⁸ whereas glycol-water⁹ and glycerol-water mixtures are more acidic than water. Despite the much lower polarity of dioxane-water mixtures, they are much more basic than comparable MeOH-water mixtures.¹⁶

The behaviour of t-BuOH-H₂O mixture is reported to be akin to dioxane-water mixtures¹⁶. DMSO-H₂O mixtures are also more basic than H₂O. In case of DMSO-H₂O mixtures, the dielectric constant change is too small to have any appreciable contribution towards the change in ΔG values, ionic solvation and change in solvent basicity accounts for the change in ΔG .

The free energy of transfer appears to be positive in all solvents except ethylene glycol+water mixtures. H₂O can thus be regarded to be in a higher free energy state in the mixed solvents. The 'electrostatic part' ΔG_{el}

$$\Delta G_{el} = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{D_s} - \frac{1}{D_w} \right] \left[\frac{1}{r_{H^+}} + \frac{1}{r_{OH^-}} \right] \quad (9)$$

is predominantly positive in going from water to mixed solvents and it probably masks the ΔG_{non-el} term which are negative. The transfer process from water is generally favoured so far as chemical interactions are concerned.¹⁶ The free energy of transfer for H⁺ ions (or cations) are reported to be negative whereas that of negative ions are positive.¹⁶

It is to be noted in this connection, that an estimation of "primary medium effect" which gives the measure of specific ion-solvent interactions are generally in the order

The interpretation of ΔH and ΔS are extremely complex in view of structural as well as electrostatic contributions.

ΔH° value (in KCal/mole) in water comes to be $13.36 \pm$ in very good agreement with the calorimetric values previously determined 13.32-13.36,²⁰⁻²⁸ though considerably lower than the previous value of 13.526²⁹ obtained potentiometrically but relatively close to recently determined potentiometric value of 13.43³⁰.

ΔH° values for different solvent systems show distinct peculiarities. While the ΔH° values in MeOH-H₂O, Glycol-water decrease as the concentration of organic component increases, ΔH° value gradually increases with ethanol, becomes maximum at about 20 wt % and then gradually decreases similar to the observations in MeOH-H₂O and glycol-water mixtures. The ΔH° values in dioxane-water and t-BuOH + H₂O show continuous increase in ΔH° but the two curves (ΔH vs wt %) are different, in case of dioxane-water, ΔH° drops at 50 wt % and increases again. In glycerol-water, ΔH° gradually decreases, becomes minimum at about 20 wt % and increases again but the ΔH° values upto 60 wt % are consistently lower than the ΔH° value in water. The ΔH° value in DMSO-H₂O is quite peculiar, ΔH° first increases upto 0.1 mole-fraction, decreases upto 0.5 mole-fraction and then increases again. The changes in ΔH° values in different mixed solvents cannot be correlated with the change in the dielectric constant indicating the importance of structural characteristics in different solvent mixtures as well as specific solute-solvent interactions.

It is interesting to note that ΔH° decreases enormously in MeOH-water mixtures¹ (from 13.34 to 6.46 KCal in 90 wt % of MeOH but the changes are very sensitive in the region 95-100%¹. Comprehensive data except methanol+water and to some extent ethanol+H₂O mixtures is lacking, but the change in ΔH° has been found to be maximum in t-BuOH+H₂O mixtures 13.34 to 18.53 in 70 wt %) compared to 16.03 in 70 wt % of dioxane+H₂O mixtures. The ΔH° values in dioxane+H₂O determined potentiometrically²⁹ are quite in disagreement with the calorimetric values.

The enthalpy of transfer ($\delta\Delta H_t$) terms for ionization of water in alcohol+H₂O mixtures [MeOH+H₂O, EtOH+H₂O (beyond 20 wt %) and ethylene glycol+water] are exothermic i. e. ionization of H₂O is favoured but the entropy of transfer terms ($T\delta\Delta S_t$) are not favourable i.e. structure forming and antitropic in character. An analysis of the $\delta\Delta H_t$ and $T\delta\Delta S_t$ show some interesting feature. In case of MeOH+H₂O mixtures, both ΔH_t and $T\delta\Delta S_t$ are negative. However, $\delta\Delta H_t > T(\delta\Delta S_t)$ i.e. entropy term (solvent ordering) predominates over enthalpy term to change $\delta\Delta G_s$. The anomalous values at low percentages of ethanol (upto 20 wt %) have been ascribed to significant structure formation³¹. Above 20 wt %, $\delta\Delta H_t > T\delta\Delta S_t$. In case of ethylene-glycol+H₂O mixtures, upto about 70 wt %, $\delta\Delta H_t < T\delta\Delta S_t$ and above $\delta\Delta H_t > T\delta\Delta S_t$, i.e. at low percentage, enthalpy term predominates over entropy term leading to increased ionization where above 70-80 wt % entropy term (solvent ordering) predominates over enthalpy term leading to decreased ionization.

The results can be visualised as follows :—

Water is a highly structured solvent and alcohols are less structured than water. In mixed solvents, there is a competition between ions and solvent molecules

for solvent ordering and structure formation. At low percentages of alcohols, alcohol molecules increase the three dimensional polymeric structure^{15,16} of water molecules i.e. solvent ordering by alcohols predominates over ions leading to a decrease in enthalpy and entropy. Above 0.1 mole-fraction of alcohols, alcohols depolymerize the three dimensional polymeric structure of water molecules leading to a decrease in order of the solvent molecules. Ions, therefore, have greater solvent ordering capability in these regions leading to a decrease in entropy.

But the picture is different in case of *t*-BuOH+H₂O and dioxane+H₂O mixtures. $\delta\Delta H_i$ values are positive (unfavourable for ionization) whereas $T\delta\Delta S_i$ values are slightly favourable in case of *t*-BuOH+H₂O mixtures (structure-breaking is favoured) but unfavourable in case of dioxane+H₂O mixtures except in the region 20-30 wt %. But in all these cases, $\delta\Delta H_i$ predominates over $T\delta\Delta S_i$ terms leading to decreased ionization. It is to be noted that the thermodynamic characteristics of dioxane+water mixtures and *t*-BuOH+H₂O mixtures are closely similar^{15,16}. Furthermore, the acidity and basicity of the different solvents and preferential solvation of ions also dominate the ionization process.

The DMSO-H₂O mixtures have been divided in three distinct zones depending on ion-solvation and structure formation^{4,5}. (i) In the region, $0 < X_{DMSO} \leq 0.12$, the $\delta\Delta H_i$ (positive) is not favourable but $T\delta\Delta S_i$ is slightly favourable; (ii) in the region $0.15 \lesssim X_{DMSO} \leq 0.50$, $\delta\Delta H_i$ is negative favouring dissociation but $T\delta\Delta S_i$ is negative and structure-forming, (iii) in the region $X_{DMSO} > 0.5$, $\delta\Delta H_i$ is unfavourable but $T(\delta\Delta S_i)$ is still favourable but structure formation is less favoured.

The results have been interpreted by Fiordiponti et al.^{4,5} on the basis that the presence of small amounts of DMSO strengthens water structure but hydration process becomes less exothermic in the region (i); in the region (ii), the solvent structure becomes more and more disorganized reaching a maximum at $X_{DMSO}=0.5$ and where protons are solvated by DMSO molecules; in the region (iii) ion-solvation becomes less exothermic due to drastic reduction in hydration of OH⁻ which is poorly solvated by DMSO.

The interpretation of the results as given by Fiordiponti et al.^{4,5} requires reexamination. DMSO is a highly associated liquid²² whereas H₂O is a highly structured solvent. At the beginning there would be a competition between the strengthening of water structure by the addition of small amounts of DMSO and the dissociation of solvent molecules to form hydrogen bonded solvent system leading to slight entropy increase in the region (i). With further addition of DMSO extensive depolymerisation of H₂O molecules as well as dissociation of DMSO molecules and subsequent formation of hydrogen-bonded DMSO-H₂O system²² (even DMSO-H₂O complexes are known) take place leading to exothermic heat of transfer. Better solvent ordering by ions and possibility of

solvation of H⁺ by DMSO leads to an entropy-decrease (region ii). Further addition of DMSO decreases the DMSO-H₂O bonded system and drastic reduction of hydration of OH⁻ leads to an entropy increase as well as enthalpy increase (region iii).

It is to be noted that order within a pure solvent is caused primarily by (a) hydrogen-bonding, (b) dipole-dipole interactions and (c) molecular shape³³. Dipole-dipole interactions leads to a greater ordering in DMSO ($\mu=3.96$) than in most hydrogen-bonded solvents.

The enthalpy term becomes favourable for ionization process in glycerol-water mixtures. This may be due to 1) enhancement for solvation facility of proton, 2) structure formation due to the addition of glycerol, 3) changes in acid-base character of the solvent, 4) glycerol molecules decrease their rotational freedom in the high electric field of an ion and contract their volume due to electrostriction leading to negative values of ΔS .³⁴

However, the evaluation of entropies of ionization by coupling apparent ΔG_s° values with determined ΔH° has been regarded to be unsatisfactory by Parsons and Rochester^{1,35}.

The ionization of water and alcohols in water+alcohol mixtures can be represented following Parsons and Rochester as

R = methyl, ethyl or butyl or ethylene glycol radical.

H⁺(S) is the solvated-proton existing in solution either as H₃O⁺ or ROH₂⁺. The apparent ionic product K_s or ΔG_s° can be represented as

$$K_s = a_{H^+} + (a_{OH^-} + a_{OR^-}) = K_W + K_R \quad (12)$$

$$\text{or } G_s^\circ = -RT \{ \ln m_{H^+} + \ln (m_{OH^-} + m_{OR^-}) \} \quad (13)$$

where K_W and K_R are the ionic products of water and alcohol respectively in a water+alcohol mixture. The measured enthalpy changes ΔH° should be correlated with ΔG° instead of ΔG_s° to have better correlation.

$$\Delta H^\circ = \alpha_{OH^-} \cdot \Delta H_w^\circ + \alpha_{OR^-} \cdot \Delta H_R \quad (14)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta G^\circ = \alpha_{OH^-} \cdot \Delta G_w^\circ + \alpha_{OR^-} \cdot \Delta G_R \quad (15)$$

$$\text{where } \alpha_{OH^-} = \frac{m_{OH^-}}{m_{OH^-} + m_{OR^-}} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{and } \alpha_{OR^-} = \frac{m_{OR^-}}{m_{OH^-} + m_{OR^-}} \quad (17)$$

Complete analysis is thus obviously difficult and the evaluation of K_W and K_R has only been made in case of methanol.^{3,5} It is apparent that the second terms in equations (14-15) would be of significance only in high percentages of alcohols. However, though ΔG° and ΔG_2° differ in magnitude but the observed trend remains almost unaltered.

Complete analysis would also require the knowledge of the equilibrium constants for the reaction

as a function of the solvent composition to know the existence of proton as H_3O^+ or ROH_2^+ which is of course lacking.

In spite of the limitations of varied nature, it can be said that the anomalous behaviour of mono-hydric alcohols are due to opposing behaviour of hydrophobic 'hydrocarbon' groups and hydrophilic 'OH' groups. The structure making and breaking effect becomes pronounced as the alcohol content increases. The anomalous behaviour is likely to shift more towards the "aqueous" behaviour as the number of hydroxylic group increases.^{1,6} However, the abnormalities of the solvent mixtures should be understood in the light of the hydrogen bond formation, ion-dipole interaction and structural aspects of these solvent mixtures. The enthalpy of ionization in different mixed solvents can be imagined to involve a number of steps. These are

- i) dissociation of bonds and energy involved in this process i.e. enthalpy change due to formation of gaseous ions.
- ii) Enthalpy change due to solvation of ions which is accompanied by the decrease in entropy due to loss of the degrees of freedom of the gaseous ions.
- iii) The structural rearrangement i.e. (a) endothermic process due to disordering of the original solvent structure leading to increase in ΔS and (b) exothermic process due to ordering of the solvent molecule around the ions leading to entropy decrease.
- iv) Change in acid-base character of the solvent.
- v) Enthalpy change due to the reaction

Quantitative evaluation of the contributions of each of these steps is necessary to explain the thermodynamic-properties of ionization of water in different mixed solvents and the specific role that the solvents play in these processes.

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